

Restriction on the Functional Form of Entropy Due to Physical Constraints?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 29, 2025

The process of obtaining a probability distribution due to the maximization of an entropy function subject to constraints is well-known in the literature. We argue, however, that the physical constraints in the problem which govern interactions seem to force the form of the entropy function. In particular, $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ ((1a)) is a general constraint, but there is usually one more constraint which is linked with conservation at the collision level such as $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((1b)). We argue that one cannot use any constraint when maximizing an entropy function, even if it is based on information from data. For example, in the case of an ideal gas, one might experimentally measure $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, but one cannot use this as a constraint for determining the distribution through maximization. In particular, we argue that one must model entropy based on the physical constraint. Given ((1a)) and ((1b)), there are multiple solutions of $p(e_i)$.

One seeks a unique solution, but there are multiple mathematical ways to obtain this even using maximization of function of p . For example, $pF(p) \rightarrow (p+dp)(F(p)+dpdF/dp)$ yields $pdF/dp=1$ if $F(p) = -e_i/T$ and one wishes only to have information about the constraints. The point we make is that the form of entropy is $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$, i.e the same form as the physical constraint. Mathematically, one could just as well maximize $p(e_i)p(e_i) F(p)$ and obtain a different distribution. We suggest that, as in previous notes, that the relevant physics is in the conservation law linked with two-body collisions (or other interactions as in a photon exciting an electron). This then restricts the form of entropy. It is no longer an arbitrary math function, but is linked directly with the average of the information function, the information being the conserved quantity. For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, there is a slight generalization which must be applied.

When applied to the Kaniadakis case, this is consistent with Kaniadakis entropy: $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln_k(p(e_i))$. We note that in the literature (1), alternative entropies are suggested for the Kaniadakis distribution. For example, one may simply create a function whose d/dp derivative yields the constraint information, but does not allow one to solve for $p(e)$ directly without knowledge of its inverse. In such a case, one is guaranteed to have d/dp equal 0, which is what happens with the entropy density proposed in (1). In this case, the maximization of entropy does not pick out a unique distribution. Rather, any distribution can be linked with an entropy function which, when maximized subject to constraints, yields the distribution. In such a case, the entropy is simply a mathematical function and not linked to a physical average of the conserved quantity.

Conservation Variable and Constraint

A constraint is a mathematical statement and is not necessarily linked with physical conservation in a problem. For example, in an ideal gas, the key idea is that one has a fixed total energy and elastic collisions:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, one constraint could be: $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((3))

This is a constraint based on the conserved quantity, energy, in collisions. We argue that this is a fundamental physical quantity, not a statistical one. To illustrate this scenario, one may consider the case in which a person measures $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{number}$ for the gas. This is a constraint, but it is not based on the conserved quantity in the problem, i.e. the quantity which describes a fundamental piece of physics which cannot be ignored. We argue that there is no point in trying to find the distribution by maximizing some function based on the $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ because this is not the underlying physical constraint (energy conservation) which must be upheld and so cannot disappear from any kind of maximization problem.

Conservation Constraints and the Entropy Function

Consider now that one has the proper physical constraints linked with the conserved quantity in a problem, i.e. ((1a)) and ((1b))

$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$

There are multiple solutions $\{p(e_i)\}$ which satisfy these two constraints, but as argued in a previous note, one wishes to have a unique distribution. The problem is that there are many ways to mathematically maximize various functions in order to find a unique distribution, but these will not be directly linked with the physical constraints in question.

For instance, because e_i is the key conserved quantity, we introduce:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((4))$$

$h(p)$ is not introduced in an arbitrary manner (it is after all only the inverse of p), but because one needs to consider the key conserved quantity e_i . One may, however, consider maximizing:

$$p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) \rightarrow (p+dp)(p+dp)(F+dp \frac{dF}{dp}) \rightarrow p \frac{dF}{dp} = 1 \quad \text{because } \sum dp_i = 0 \quad ((5))$$

In other words, one may create any number of math expressions based on $F(p(e_i))$ which when varied yield 0 based on the differentials of even the physical constraints.

We suggest that entropy must be a special function, which when maximized based on the differentials of the physical constraints (physical meaning dealing with conserved quantities), yields zero. In particular, this function must be based on the constraint equation of the conserved quantity, assuming that there is only one in the problem. Thus, we suggest that one use:

$$p(e) h(p(e_i)) \quad ((6)) \quad \text{if } p(e_i) \text{ is in fact the probability used in the constraint.}$$

In the Tsallis case, one uses $p(e_i)$ power q in the physical constraint linked to the conserved quantity and so this same $p(e_i)$ power q appears in ((6)).

The notion of entropy seems to be driven by physics, i.e. the conserved quantity e_i .

If some other physical quantity is conserved, then that may be used instead of e_i . The point is that the scheme is linked with a conserved quantity.

Kaniadakis Case

This brings one to the Kaniadakis case. The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution already represents one which satisfies:

$$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p(e_i) \frac{dh}{dp(e_i)} = 1 \quad ((7b))$$

This is based on the constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ ((8))

Even though the Kaniadakis situation uses the same constraints, it does not follow from maximization if one uses the prescribed physical formalism for entropy based on the physical (conserved quantity) constraint. In such a case, one has:

$$S_k \text{ density} = 1/2k (p(e_i)^{1+k} - p(e_i)^{1-k}) \quad ((8))$$

This has been given by Kaniadakis as noted in (1). In (1), however, an alternative S_k entropy is proposed. (1) uses:

$$\ln_k(p(e_i)) = 1/2k (p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k}) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is then integrated and added to $b_k p(e_i)$ so that when one takes the derivative multiplied by $dp(e_i)$, one obtains:

$$\ln_k(p(e_i)) dp(e_i) + b_k d(p(e_i)) \quad ((10))$$

These two terms sum to 0 giving the impression of a maximization of entropy consistent with the constraints in the problem. The point is that one simply integrates a function and then takes its derivative and so this scheme can be applied to any $h(p(e_i))$. Thus, a unique $p(e_i)$ is not obtained as one does not base the maximization on the physical constraint which governs the interactions in the problem, we argue.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

The Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases are a little more general, but are still based on the idea of an entropy function linked with the $p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ term, but with an added term. In other words, the idea of conservation of energy is still key and entropy is not an arbitrary function, but

is built around the $e_i h(p(e_i))$ form. In particular, we consider the Fermi-Dirac case because one simply changes - to + to obtain the Bose-Einstein result.

From reaction-balance:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((11a))$$

$$p(e_1)(1-p(e_3)) p(e_2)(1-p(e_4)) = p(e_3)(1-p(e_1)) p(e_4)(1-p(e_2)) \quad ((11b))$$

$$\text{Thus: } h(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) = -e_i/T \quad ((12))$$

If one were to simply create: $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$, then taking $d/dp(e_i)$ does not yield the two constraint differentials. (There is actually more information here than the two constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, namely that idea that one can only have one fermion in the e_i level). This extra piece of information complicates matters, but the idea of entropy built around the average energy should still hold, we argue. One may propose for entropy:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) + F(p(e_i)) \quad ((13))$$

$$\text{It turns out that } F(p(e_i)) = \ln(1-p(e_i)) \quad ((14)) \text{ from (2)}$$

This result is slightly more complicated, but is based on the extra information in the problem, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that entropy seems to be a function representing the average of the information of the conserved quantity in interactions in a problem if the constraints are simply $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. (In the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, matters are a little more complicated as there is extra information than the two constraints, but the conservation of e is still key.) As a result, we argue that one cannot create arbitrary entropy density functions, but requires one linked to the average of the information which in the MB case is $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ and in the Tsallis $p(e_i)$ power q $\ln_q(p(e_i))$. Thus, entropy is not simply an arbitrary math function to be extremized, but is linked to physics, i.e the average of information, where the information is a conserved quantity in an interaction (as one example).

References

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